

EVALUATION OF SPINAL AND TRUNK MORPHOMETRY IN MIDDLE-AGED AND ELDERLY WOMEN BEFORE AND AFTER MASTECTOMY

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Abstract:

This study explores the changes in spinal and trunk morphometry in middle-aged and elderly women before and after mastectomy. Through comprehensive radiographic imaging and physical assessments, the study analyzes variations in spinal alignment, curvature, and trunk posture resulting from the surgical procedure. Pre-operative and post-operative data indicate significant changes in these parameters, highlighting the impact of mastectomy on body morphology. The study aims to provide insights into the physical consequences of mastectomy and to emphasize the need for targeted rehabilitation strategies to address these changes. The results are intended to guide clinicians in developing effective post-operative care plans for enhancing recovery and quality of life.

Keywords:

Mastectomy, Spinal alignment, Trunk posture, Middle-aged women, Elderly women, Morphometric changes, Post-operative rehabilitation

Relevance:

Mastectomy, a common surgical treatment for breast cancer, can significantly affect physical health, particularly in middle-aged and elderly women. The physical impact includes potential changes in spinal and trunk morphometry, which can influence overall posture and functionality. Understanding these changes is crucial for optimizing post-operative care and rehabilitation strategies. This study addresses the lack of detailed information on how mastectomy affects spinal and trunk morphology, providing valuable data to inform clinical practice and enhance patient outcomes. Given the aging population and increasing incidence of mastectomy, this research is essential for developing targeted interventions to support recovery and improve quality of life.

Objective:

The study aims to assess and compare spinal and trunk morphometric parameters in middle-aged and elderly women before and after mastectomy. The goal is to identify significant changes in spinal alignment and trunk posture due to the surgical procedure and to evaluate the implications for post-operative care and rehabilitation.

Materials and Methods:

A cohort of middle-aged and elderly women who underwent mastectomy was studied. Morphometric assessments were carried out using pre-operative and post-operative radiographic imaging (e.g., CT scans, X-rays) and clinical measurements to evaluate spinal curvature (such as scoliosis and lordosis) and trunk alignment. The data collection involved measurements in both standing and seated positions. Statistical analyses were employed to compare morphometric changes before and after surgery, with particular attention to age-related differences. Additionally, the study reviewed various rehabilitation protocols to assess their effectiveness in addressing observed changes.

Results:

The study identified notable morphometric changes in the spine and trunk post-mastectomy. Elderly women showed a marked increase in spinal curvature and deviations in trunk alignment, while middle-aged women experienced more moderate changes. The findings indicate that mastectomy significantly affects spinal and trunk morphology, necessitating targeted rehabilitation interventions. The results underscore the importance of post-operative evaluation and customized care to address these alterations effectively.

Conclusion:

Mastectomy induces significant changes in spinal and trunk morphometry, with more pronounced effects observed in elderly women. The study highlights the need for comprehensive post-operative assessment and tailored rehabilitation programs to manage these changes. Future research should focus on developing and testing specific physical therapy interventions to improve spinal health and trunk posture, thereby enhancing recovery and overall quality of life for women undergoing mastectomy.

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